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Community curation of kinetic data to support metabolic models through semantic web technology

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Abstract

Motivation: Large portions of biomedical data and knowledge are captured in various databases and research papers leading to heterogeneous knowledge resources. Furthermore, these resources often have limited capabilities to interact with each other, leaving researchers to wrangle, clean, and manually integrate data relevant to their projects. Specifically for metabolic modeling approaches, kinetic data is available in different databases and primary literature in a non-harmonized manner, complicating data analysis for systems biology and systems pharmacology approaches. Collecting the data in these databases individually as one coherent structure is performed by experienced database curators, who possess thorough expertise in the collected and modeled content for their database. This process can be aided with community curation efforts, where less experienced curators such as undergraduate students, post-graduates, and wet lab scientists could be useful to provide valuable data annotations. Community curation can also be a valuable resource to integrate data scattered over multiple platforms, collecting related knowledge in one machine-readable overview. This study describes a workflow for the community curation of kinetic data to support pathway models (PWMs) and subsequent capturing of this data into a semantic web technology Resource Description Framework (RDF). Pathway knowledge on Inherited Metabolic Disorders (IMDs) was collected, since for this class of rare diseases often a good understanding of the molecular mechanism is available in the literature, but not in databases. Furthermore, IMDs can be difficult to diagnose and treatment options are scarcely available.

Results: Our approach led to several new PWMs for various inherited metabolic disorder (IMD) classes supported by available kinetic information from the BRENDA Enzyme Database, STRENDA, SABIO-RK, IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY, UniProt, and primary literature from PubMed. The manually collected data was converted to a semantic format supported by automated curation. The script created for this conversion is a showcase of how automated curation can maximize manual curation efforts. By capturing the data in a semantic RDF model, researchers can easily assess which interactions in a model of interest are missing data, shortening wet-lab time. Furthermore, the RDF data can be reused on new pathways that include overlapping metabolic interactions. Last, the collected data could be used in novel approaches to identify, diagnose, and contribute to discovering treatments for rare metabolic disorders such as IMDs.

Availability and implementation: All data and code reported herein are open science and available for download at github.com/BiGCAT-UM/KinRDF.

8.1 Introduction

The growing amount of published biomedical data present is difficult to keep up with, both in volume and diversity. This issue is also faced by databases facilitating (multi-)omics approaches, which depend on variety, velocity, and volume (the three V's of 'big data') to provide relevant data analysis [1]. Another critical aspect is the quality of data, which requires thorough expertise to verify [2]; the volume of a database is in itself not a good measure of qualitative content and can lead to downstream data analysis issues (also referred to as "garbage in – garbage out") [3]. Several automated approaches exist to curate the knowledge into a machine-readable format, such as text mining on the corpus of papers [4, 5], text mining on figures within papers [6, 7], and algorithms aiming to find: similarities between genomics regions in different species [8], protein-protein interactions [9], and relating chemical compounds based on structural similarities for drug discovery [10].

Currently, there is no full overview available of all metabolic reactions that can occur in the human body for data analysis or data integration in pathway models (PWMs). Several pathway databases [11–16], Genome-Scale Metabolic Models (GEMs) [17–19], and reaction databases [20–23] try to obtain an (as complete as possible) overview of these reactions. All these databases contain overlapping but also unique content regarding their biochemical reaction content, and some are integrating data from multiple databases; combining equivalent pathways in one unique model is needed to avoid redundant information as well as provide reproducible results for pathway analysis [24]. Several resources exist aiming to combine different databases for (multi-)omics analysis [25–29]. However, not all issues can be resolved to date, e.g. the influence of ambiguous names and identifier annotations (specifically problematic for small molecules such as metabolites), minimal overlap between reactions for seemingly similar pathways due to minute differences in substrate or product annotations, and correctly integrating parent-child pathways [30–35].

Adding new knowledge to pathway (and other biology-related) databases is performed by researchers who acquire and integrate knowledge from various resources into data repositories. These are also referred to as database curators in the field of biology (or biocurators), who add value to the repository by annotating and connecting research data [36]. Due to the heterogeneous and diverse nature of biological data, biocuration requires thorough expertise in the content curated [37], as well as innovative ways to capture, represent, and display the collected information. Most researchers are experts in specific domains rather than generalists, and collaborations between research fields and domains are required to make the most use of the existing experimental outcomes from omics data. To aid in the curation process, community curation might be a solution, with ample successful examples [38–47].

Unfortunately, tools and databases to enable community curation by letting authors of (biomedical) publications capture their information in a machine-readable format and share this as open-access content with others is rare. A tool that does

allow for community curation is PathVisio (pathvisio.org) [48], allowing users to model biological pathways in a machine-readable manner supporting OMICS data and network analysis. The format behind these pathways is described in the Graphical Pathway Markup Language (GPML), which is flexible enough to accommodate drawing detailed biological interactions as well as overview pathways while maintaining the captured information readable for automated extraction (GPML is a subclass of the XML file format [49]). These pathways are shared with others on WikiPathways (wikipathways.org) [15] under the CC0 license, allowing every researcher to (re)use and modify the PWMs. Other downstream usage of the content captured through WikiPathways is through sharing the data using semantic web technologies.

Semantic web technologies are a standard to create interconnected information on the internet that can be interpreted by computers, by making use of semantic representations of data through formal descriptions of knowledge as a set of concepts within a domain and the relationships between these concepts (ontologies) or the Resource Description Framework (RDF) format, which uses a three-part representation of information in a 'subject-predicate/ relationship-object' structure. Data encoded as RDF can be used to create structured data that is interlinked with other data allowing for integrative semantic queries (linked (open) data), allowing for automatic connections with other data in the same format [50]. This approach does require the use of a unique code to classify the represented entity in an internal or online tool, or knowledgebase (stable identifiers) [51], as well as training researchers to use the data model and links between different databases captured through different models for their RDF data [52].

Biologically-centered databases can greatly benefit from RDF to represent their data [53], which can also be leveraged by downstream bioinformatics applications [54]. Furthermore, using linked open data approaches can aid in removing the interoperability thresholds that currently exist between databases, since most of these use different formats, entity annotations, and schemes, leading to a fragmented and heterogeneous data landscape [55]. These issues specifically hold for (computational) metabolic modeling, which is used to study the dynamic behaviors of complex systems. These models can suffer from reusability issues through annotation issues (different identifiers or names are used), as well as the use of different modeling formats, and issues with integrating several models [34, 56–58]. Machine readable pathways can be used as a basis for these metabolic models, by complementing the models with kinetic data. This approach is essential to investigate the re-purposing of existing drugs for (rare) metabolic diseases or the synergies of drug combinations [59]. Also, fluxomics studies are essential to understand and ultimately treat metabolic (rare) disorders [60, 61]. Connecting the existing pathway knowledge with kinetic data directly from databases and publications requires a machine-readable model describing the data that is straightforward for (novel) users.

These models are parameterized with kinetic data (molecular reaction rates), to study the flow through a system. These enzyme kinetics can be measured

in vitro by the use of enzyme assays [62]. This knowledge can then be used to resemble the *in vivo* situation, by closely matching the conditions between both and inferring information for the latter, also known as the *ex vivo* approach. Enzyme assays provide two relevant parameters in this context: the maximum uptake rate or velocity of a substrate, V_{max} , and the Michaelis constant, K_m , also known as the substrate concentration at which the reaction rate is 50% of the V_{max} as a measure of the substrate affinity for an enzyme has for its substrate [63]. To achieve representative measurements for the *in vivo* situation, standardization of experiments and assay conditions are critical [64, 65]. Unfortunately, sparse kinetic data limits its downstream application in fluxomics data analysis approaches [66, 67].

This paper aims to describe our approach to creating a kinetic data model using the semantic web format RDF, applying this model to existing data, and providing examples of how to use the data captured with the model. With the proposed model, a new standard for leveraging experimental kinetic, metabolic reactions, OMICS data, pathways, and metabolic modeling approaches has been created. The kinetic RDF data model provides a directed and labeled graph data format to create a network of linked data. The model itself was tested using a community curation approach, by training several students from a Biomedical Science Bachelor program to parameterize a PWM related to inherited metabolic disorders (IMDs). The data in the model can be retrieved (queried) with the RDF query language SPARQL. Our approach is in line with other Linked Open Data [68] initiatives (e.g. Wikidata [47], by providing structured and semantically enriched data which can be interlinked with other data. Furthermore, the data can be used in other applications such as Genome Scale Metabolic Modeling [69] or to construct a weighted metabolic network [70].

8.2 Methods

8.2.1 Community curation for kinetic parameters of pathway models

The community curation consisted of three independent groups; the first group (five students) was recruited in 2019, the second (six students), and the third group (five students) in 2022. Each student kept an individual logbook (hosted as a Markdown file on GitHub) and created at least one kinetic pathway model, based on the following process as depicted in Figure 8.1: 1. Follow the online WikiPathways Academy (academy.wikipathways.org) [71]; 2. Select a chapter from the clinical genetics reference book *Physician's guide to the diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of inherited metabolic diseases* [72]; 3. Create a PWM for a Figure in this chapter (using the methodology described in Section 8.2.1); 4. Upload the model to WikiPathways for peer review by another student and the project mentor; 5. Improve the model with the peer-review comments (added in the GitHub issue tracker), and extend the model with additional literature; 6. Find kinetic data for all proteins in the model, and add these to the provided template (see section 8.2.1); 7. Perform a basic data visualization with the created model (e.g. transcriptomics or metabolomics data) combined with the kinetic

data in the network tool Cytoscape [73] using the WikiPathways App [74] to ensure basic machine readability of the collected data.

Figure 8.1: Community curation workflow. Seven steps were required to create pathway models with corresponding kinetic data.

Furthermore, students were asked to read key publications related to kinetic data analysis [59]; WikiPathways: [group 1] [71], [group 2 and 3] [15]; RDF modeling: [group 1 only] W3C RDF 1.1 Primer); pathway creation and curation: [groups 2 and 3 only] [75]); and IMDs [groups 2 and 3 only] [60]).

Pathway models creation

Machine-readable versions of metabolic pathways related to IMDs were created using the pathway editor and curation tool PathVisio (version 3.3.0) [48]. Protein DataNodes were annotated with Human Reviewed (SwissProt/gold star) UniProt IDs [76], which

linked to potentially relevant Rhea IDs [77] for the metabolic conversion interactions. The Rhea IDs were manually curated regarding the directionality of the reaction and stereochemistry on the substrate and product of the reactions (if available). The information on substrate and products from Rhea was used to annotate the Metabolite DataNodes with a ChEBI ID [78]. For the disorders, no DataNode type was available, thus, these were modeled through textLabels [79] and annotated with a URL from OMIM [80].

Kinetic data collection

The collected data was retrieved according to the following criteria:

1. Protein identification; data needed to be available on the protein level matching the UniProt entries in the PWM to the HGNC nomenclature name using the identifier mapping tool BridgeDb [81].
2. Data provenance; the HGNC symbols needed to be present in one of the following databases: the BRENDA Enzyme Database [22], STRENDA [82], SABIO-RK [21], IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY [83], and UniProt [76]. If primary literature references were provided for the data entry, their PubMed [84] identifiers were retrieved.
3. Relevant species; data was first collected for human (*Homo sapiens*), mouse (*Mus musculus*) or rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) entries, or other vertebrates if the former three were not available. Data originating from plants were excluded from the data collection.
4. Conditions; pH levels and temperature data should be close to *in vivo* conditions, e.g. pH (close to) 7 and a temperature of (approximately) 37°C.
5. cell cultures; entries describing a wild type or natural recombinant enzyme were favored. Values specific for mutations (SNPs) related to the IMDs included in the PWMs were also collected if available.

The kinetic data was captured using a tab-separated structure and saved as a text file (.txt format). The template included the relevant parameters as column headers and two example rows with data, as depicted in Table 8.1. Units relevant for the kinetic parameters were based on [59], and identified as the Michaelis constant (K_m in mM), the turnover number or first-order rate constant (K_{cat} in s^{-1}), the catalytic efficiency of enzymes or second-order rate constant (K_{cat}/K_m in $M^{-1}s^{-1}$), Temperature (in degree Celsius or °C), and pH (unitless). Individual entries should be listed on a new row, and unknown values should be left empty or denoted with a hyphen '-'. Students were instructed to leave the columns in the template file in the same order, to allow for downstream processing.

Table 8.1: Kinetic data template (version 1.0) as provided to the community curators.

Parameter	Data Example 1	Data Example 2
EnzymePW	Aminocyclase 2	LPL
ApprovedEnzymeName	-	lipoprotein lipase
E.C.number	3.5.1.15	3.1.1.34
UniProt	P45381	P06863
Ensembl	-	-
Rhea ID	RHEA:14167	triacylglycerol + H ₂ O = diacylglycerol + a carboxylate
CHEBI ID	16953	59238
K_m (mM)	0,163	1,12
K_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	37,5	-
K_{cat}/K_m (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	-	-
pH	7,4	-
Temperature (Celsius)	37	-
Additional Conditions	-	-
Organism	Homo sapiens	Gallus gallus
PMID	18280251	11249004
Database	BRENDA: 668640	BRENDA

8.2.2 Kinetic data model RDF creation

An initial RDF framework to convert the kinetic data from the template structure was created together with the students from group 1 (see Figure 8.2 for a visual representation). The RDF model creation was scripted using Python (v.3.8.15) [85], tested in RStudio (version 2022.07.1+554) [86], and available at github.com/BigCAT-UM/KinRDF. The script was tested on the data collected by group 1 for five PWMs, including a Quality Control (QC) report which reports a summary of the data captured through the RDF, data not conforming to expected standards using regular expressions (regex), and entries requiring curation due to missing data. Each entry (row) is first harmonized for prefixes from Rhea and ChEBI [columns 6 and 7 of the template]. To identify unique entries in the kinetics data, a Substrate-Enzyme-Reaction (SER) identifier is created (combining the identifiers from ChEBI, UniProt, and Rhea). Entries with missing data for the three required identifiers (ChEBI, UniProt, and Rhea) are removed [columns 4, 6, and 7], as well as those missing both of the provenance columns (PubMed identifier or Database name) [columns 15 and 16]. The regex first test for the structure of the ChEBI, UniProt, and Rhea identifiers, to support the creation of a SER identifier. This identifier is then connected to separate entities for the substrate, enzyme, and reaction using a "has part" relationship (SIO_000028), while the kinetic data is added to a measurement entity using the "has attribute" predicate (SIO_000008). The substrate object connects to the original ChEBI identifier and WikiPathways RDF [87] ChEBI identifier (wp:bdbChEBI). The enzyme information contains the original UniProt entry, a textlabel for the protein name, a link to the Enzyme Code Nomenclature [88], an Ensembl identifier [89], a connection to the WikiPathways RDF GeneProduct and Protein mappings (wp:bdbEnsembl and wp:bdbUniprot), and a link to the Bioregistry platform [90] (bioregistry:hasDbXref). The reaction knowledge is linked to the Rhea RDF identifier (rh:accession) and the WikiPathways RDF Rhea identifier (wp:bdbRhea). If the reaction was not represented in Rhea, the SER identifier included a link to a reaction equation (rh:equation), which was captured in a string representation (e.g. "Cysteinyglycine = cysteine"^^xsd:string). The kinetic data measurement values included the K_m (SER:hasKm), K_{cat} (SER:hasKcat), and K_{cat}/K_m (SER:hasKcatKm), as well as data relevant to the specific measurement: Temperature (wdt:P2076), pH (SER:hasPh), additionally reported conditions e.g. mutation cell-lines (dcterms:description), the organism name (wp:organismName), and provenance ('dcterms:references' for publications and 'dc:source' for databases). All numerical values were tested using a regex (with a dot-decimal separator), organism names against a list of vertebrates names in Latin and their common English nomenclature. The provenance items are checked against a list of supported databases ('brenda', 'sabio', 'guide to pharmacology', 'strenda', 'uniprot') and the PubMed IDs for numerical values (without a decimal separator). If multiple values are available for both (and separated with a semicolon), these are added as individual entries in the RDF.

The final RDF data is validated using the RDF NTriples/Turtle validator (version 1.1.1) to verify a correct syntax (github.com/IDLabResearch/TurtleValidator).

8.2.3 Validation of community curation for kinetic RDF data model

The seven kinetic data files from groups 2 and 3 were sequentially added to a validation sub-folder to check the Kinetic data model RDF creation script for errors, and the resulting RDF for validity. Changes to the source code were documented using GitHub. After the script had been updated, the entries reported in the QC report were checked manually and uploaded to GitHub. As additional validation steps, the created RDF data was compared against Shape Expressions [91], which were automatically validated using GitHub Actions.

8.2.4 Data querying

To construct an overview of the PWMs included in this study, the WikiPathways SPARQL Endpoint (available at <https://sparql.wikipathways.org>) was queried on the data from May of 2023 (WikiPathways RDF 20230510). Query 12 obtained results from both the WP-RDF and the GPMP-RDF; the former includes the title, identifier of the pathway, number of proteins, metabolites, metabolic interaction identifiers, metabolic interactions where the Rhea ID is missing, and the latter the disease annotations which are stored in the GPML RDF-version. UNION-statements were used for a fast response, to avoid the aggregation of many individual results in between the subsections of the query which were not related (e.g. the number of proteins and number of metabolites were not related to each other, however to one PWM). A VALUES-statement was used to only query the models relevant for this study: group 1: WP4518, WP4519, WP4521, WP4522, WP4523, WP4524; group 2: WP5169, WP5171, WP5176, WP5189, WP5190, WP5193; group 3: WP5166, WP5172, WP5173, WP5175, WP5178, WP5195. Note that during the time of querying, WP5172 (Iron metabolism disorders) was not part of the WikiPathways monthly RDF download yet. The Kinetic RDF data can be queried using a local Virtuoso SPARQL endpoint [92] as a Docker (for documentation see the GitHub repository).

```

#Variable selection
SELECT DISTINCT (str(?title) as ?pathwayName) ?PWID
(count(distinct ?geneProduct) AS ?GenesInPWs)
(count(distinct ?protein) AS ?ProteinsInPWs)
(count(distinct ?metaboliteNode) AS ?MetabolitesInPWs)
(count(distinct ?interactionID) AS ?RheaInPWs)
(count(distinct ?interactionMissing) AS ?NoRheaInPWs)
(count(distinct ?omim) as ?diseaseIDs)

WHERE {

  VALUES ?PWID { "WP4518" "WP4519" "WP4521" "WP4522" "WP4523" "WP4524" #group1
                  "WP5169" "WP5171" "WP5176" "WP5189" "WP5190" "WP5193" #group2
                  "WP5166" "WP5172" "WP5173" "WP5175" "WP5178" "WP5195" #group3
                }

  ?pathway dcterms:identifier ?PWID. #Obtain the ID
  ?pathway wp:isAbout ?gplmrdf_ID . #find the corresponding GPML link
  ?pathway dc:title ?title . #Obtain the title

  {
    ?geneProduct dcterms:isPartOf ?pathway . #Only those part of PW
    ?geneProduct a wp:GeneProduct . #Filter for GeneProduct DataNodes
  }
  UNION
  {
    ?protein dcterms:isPartOf ?pathway . #Only those part of PW
    ?protein a wp:Protein . #Filter for Protein DataNodes
  }
  UNION
  {
    ?metaboliteNode a wp:Metabolite . #Filter for Metabolite DataNodes
    ?metaboliteNode dcterms:isPartOf ?pathway . #Only those part of PW
  }
  UNION
  {
    OPTIONAL(?interaction wp:bdbRhea ?interactionID . #Find interactions with a Rhea ID
    ?interaction dcterms:isPartOf ?pathway .) #Only those part of PW
  }
  UNION
  {
    OPTIONAL(?interactionMissing dcterms:isPartOf ?pathway . #Find additional interactions
    ?interactionMissing rdf:type wp:Conversion . #That are of type 'metabolic conversion'
    FILTER NOT EXISTS {?interactionMissing wp:bdbRhea ?interactionID .} #Without a Rhea ID
  }
  UNION {
    ?diseaseNode dcterms:isPartOf ?gplmrdf_ID . #Only check for matching pathways
    ?diseaseNode rdf:type gpml:Label . #Only include textLabels
    ?diseaseNode gpml:href ?omim . #That have an href attribute
    FILTER regex(?omim, "omim.org", "i") #Only keep hrefs if they contain 'omim.org'
  }
} ORDER BY ASC(?pathway)

```

Code Example 12: SPARQL Query to obtain the number of proteins, metabolites, and metabolic interactions for the PWMs specific to this project.

8.3 Results

8.3.1 Community curation for kinetic parameters of pathway models

All community curators followed the WikiPathways Academy (according to their log-books), and used a chapter from the clinical genetics reference book to create a pathway model (PWM). All models were uploaded to WikiPathways and curated through a community peer review (using the GitHub issue trackers of their respective projects). After the curation comments were addressed, the project mentor awarded the PWMs the "Approved for Data Analysis" quality tag on WikiPathways, meaning that the model was in sufficient shape for downstream analysis applications. Several students could not load their kinetic data files into Cytoscape at first (for example by adding special characters such as °C in their file), which was changed manually in their respective files. This also led to updating the column headers of the template, to indicate the units for each column. The students from groups 2 and 3 needed to submit an individual report describing the project and analyses (which was not mandatory for the students from group 1 in 2019). Not all reports included a data visualization with the gathered kinetic data. Out of the total eleven students in groups 2 and 3, only seven kinetic data files were submitted in their GitHub respective projects that could be used for the validation of the RDF data model.

8.3.2 Pathway models creation

Each community curator created a PWM, which contained enzymes linked to genetically inheritable metabolic disorders (IMDs). Table 8.2 (based on Query 12) lists the biological content of each pathway in terms of proteins, metabolites, interactions, and disorders covered, and in which curation round these was obtained.

The knowledge captured was curated on individual reactions by performing a comparison on the chemical structure of the product of one step to the substrate (starting metabolite) of the next step if each step could be catalyzed by one (or more) enzymes, and if this step was described in an interaction database (with primary literature). If available, the individual interactions between a substrate and product were annotated with a reaction identifier. The unique combination of substrate, enzyme, and product was used to collect kinetic data.

8.3.3 Kinetic Data Collection

The data relevant for kinetic modeling purposes were based on [59] and extended with parameters needed to connect this data to the PWMs from WikiPathways, as well as to the metabolic interaction database Rhea [77]. Both of these knowledge bases individually expose their data in an RDF model. The community curation groups reported several issues with the collection of this data, some databases for example used their internal IDs for publications instead of the PubMed IDs directly. Another

Table 8.2: Pathways and relevant content in the WikiPathways RDF, based on Query 12. Uniqueness counts based on unification to Rhea IDs (metabolic reactions), and OMIM URLs (IMDs). Metabolic conversions that could not be connected to a Rhea ID are added in the respective column; * indicates no kinetics data was found for this specific PWM. The final column indicates to which curation group the PWM belongs.

Pathway Name	PWID	Genes	Proteins	Metabolites	Rhea	Rhea Missing	IMDs	Group
Gamma-glutamyl cycle for the biosynthesis and degradation of glutathione, including diseases	WP4518	2	6	11	7	0	5	1
Cerebral organic acidurias, including diseases	WP4519	2	8	28	10	8	5	1
Glycosylation and related congenital defects	WP4521	1	25	29	18	2	21	1
Metabolic pathway of LDL, HDL and TG, including diseases *	WP4522	10	17	5	0	0	17	1
Classical pathway of steroidogenesis with glucocorticoid and mineralocorticoid metabolism	WP4523	13	22	30	29	15	14	1
Alternative pathway of fetal androgen synthesis	WP4524	12	13	18	14	9	7	1
Glyoxylate metabolism	WP5166	1	14	16	9	2	3	3
Hemesynthesis defects and porphyrias	WP5169	9	0	18	2	8	10	2
Leukotriene metabolic pathway	WP5171	13	4	19	11	7	5	2
Disorders of galactose metabolism	WP5173	13	3	10	3	3	13	3
Disorders in ketone body synthesis	WP5175	0	5	13	1	2	4	3
Disorders of bile acid synthesis and biliary transport	WP5176	18	6	44	4	7	17	2
Disorders of fructose metabolism	WP5178	14	0	17	3	1	14	3
Copper metabolism	WP5189	4	0	2	0	0	5	2
Creatine pathway	WP5190	4	2	18	5	2	6	2
Cholesterol synthesis disorders	WP5193	18	12	17	3	3	18	2
Disorders in ketolysis	WP5195	0	5	8	1	2	3	3

example of issues was the use of ranges for Temperatures or pH, as well as data not being available for vertebrates for specific enzymes. Regarding the use of the .txt template, the students advised to populate the file with content from the pathway model to save time on the annotations, in combination with providing the example data.

8.3.4 Kinetic data model RDF creation

The complete kinetic RDF data model is visualized in Figure 8.2. Prefixes within the model were derived from defined vocabularies as recommended by the W3C (<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query>). By including these additional parameters (e.g. identifiers for these databases), data can be linked together with so-called federated queries.

The dataset of the five files from group 1 contained 248 lines of information. Not all entries contained a correct Enzyme Nomenclature code (244), or an Ensembl ID (111). Several reactions were present in Rhea (172); the remaining reactions were expressed using chemical equations (76). Kinetic parameterization data was available for unique SERs regarding the K_m (164), K_{cat} (49), K_{cat}/K_m (50), Temperature (152), and pH (159). Furthermore, additional conditions were reported (131), and most data was connected to an organism name (229). Last, the provenance was added to the model as PubMed IDs (241) or database names (248).

Based on the regex and other data-format check mechanisms in the RDF-creation script, four entries contained an Enzyme Nomenclature code not adhering to standards (1.3.1.B13 and 1.1.1.B40, the latter used for three entries). Also, several species names listed were not included in the model (which only focused on well-studied vertebrates). Seven entries were not included in the model due to data missing (from either ChEBI, UniProt, or Rhea), and another seven entries were disregarded due to a lack of provenance information (on both the PubMed ID and database name). The proposed kinetic RDF data model allows to querying of the data in a structured format, as well as interlinking the data with other online resources through the semantic web.

Figure 8.2: Visualization of RDF model to describe kinetic data. For each data entry (labeled "Substrate Enzyme Reaction"), subjects and objects are connected with a predicate (depicted above the connecting arrows). Data relevant for kinetic modeling purposes in blue, protein identifiers in green, provenance of the data in red. Interoperability with the WikiPathways RDF model in yellow and Rhea RDF in purple, with the proposed predicates in pink boxes. Data belonging to multiple categories contain several background colors. Units are provided when relevant for kinetic data in pink, outlined in red. Additional information needed for machine readability of data (e.g. textual strings) is added by the model, represented in cyan.

8.3.5 Validation of community curation for kinetic RDF data model

The seven kinetic data files from groups 2 and 3 were used to validate the model and make adjustments if needed. Each step in the validation process is described in Table 8.3. Each file was evaluated separately, and changes to the source code were

documented using GitHub. As a first result, the instructions for future curators should include a step to name the file using the PWM ID, to avoid having duplicate entries

Table 8.3: For each submitted file, the different issues encountered are described, as well as the applied solutions (linked to GitHub commits). The last column reflects how many SER entries were added for each file. *: Manual curation of the file was required to complete the validation process.

PWM ID	Issues?	Fixes
WP5166.txt	The script runs without interruptions, RDF not valid 1. Provenance missing for alternative database names 2. Multiple values for provenance with different separator (, iso ;) 3. Spaced before prefix ('RHEA:', 'CHEBI:') and actual ID 4. Chemical names in substrate column together with ChEBI IDs 5. Species names with two capitals (e.g. 'Rattus Norvegicus') 6. Common bacteria (without space) in abbreviation ('E.coli')	1. Added alternative names list for databases (#9536231) 1. Added databases entries not recognized to Error Report (#211c6ad) 2. Added two separator types for Provenance info (#9536231) 3. Remove spaces between prefix and ID (#211c6ad) 4. Remove chemical names in ChEBI ID column (#211c6ad) 4. Remove space after ChEBI IDs before matching (#13b607b) 4. Update template with substrate name column (#19fa56e) 5. Convert species names from users to lower cases before matching (#13b607b) 6. Added common bacteria species, alternative name, space separator (#13b607b) 6. Add species name from approved list (#13b607b)
WP5169.xlsx	Script runs without interruptions, no data added 1. File in .xlsx format, not .txt 2. Provenance not according to the template (e.g. 'Brenda: 736819')	1. Read in .xlsx format files (#21cc9a1) 2. Always add a statement if the provenance is not according to standard (#21cc9a1) 2. Remove irrelevant provenance data (#7f2d5f6) 2. Add warning if multiple separators are used in one entry (#7f2d5f6) 2. Add provenance data from restricted list (#5b42b90)
WP5172.xlsx	Script runs without interruptions, RDF valid	No changes required
WP5173.xlsx	The script shows error, RDF not valid 1. Error: Km values include strings (e.g. 'same as above') 2. Different order of columns than expected* 3. Double provenance for PubMed and Databases 4. Empty values represented with '' 5. EC-codes including 'EC'	1. Report non-numerical parameters to QC (#19fa56e) 2. Report files in QC with different column names than expected (#d884459) 2. Manually resolved changed column names issue (#b521bc1) 3. Include split items for both provenance items (#f7fbab3) 4. Remove '' as empty value representation (#b521bc1) 5. Remove 'EC:' for Enzyme Nomenclature data (#9a074bb)
WP5176.txt	The script shows error, syntax is valid 1. UnicodeDecodeError* 2. Different column names than expected* 3. Empty values represented with '' 4. Reactome Reaction IDs (e.g. 'R-HSA-193533') used iso Rhea 5. Misspelled species name (e.g. 'Homo sapien')	1. Flag files with UnicodeDecodeError in QC report (#03be807) 1. Manually removed not UTF-8 encoded characters (#03be807) 2. Manually resolved changed column names issue (#03be807) 3. Remove '' as empty value representation (#d75b384) 4. Add reaction IDs starting with 'R-HSA' to QC (#0c59774) 5. Convert 'Homo sapien' to correct spelling (#0c59774)
WP5189.csv	The script runs without interruptions, no data added 1. File in .csv format, not .txt 2. EC-codes including 'EC' 3. ChEBI IDs include two values (separated with '/')	1. Read in .csv format files (#f03cdb7) 2. Remove 'EC' for Enzyme Nomenclature data (#d194513) 3. Add entries with multiple ChEBI IDs to QC report (#cb81c68)
WP5190.csv	The script runs without interruptions, RDF valid 1. .csv file with tab as separator 2. Reaction IDs contain 'Rhea:'	1. Data is read correctly, no change needed (#0470f12) 2. Remove 'Rhea:' and other spellings (#539b1ff)

and trace back entries needing curation. Furthermore, the Kinetic Data collection Template was adapted to include the substrate name as an individual column, as well as to include the units for all measurement parameters clearly in the column headings (Template 2.0). Overall, the main issues found through the validation process were related to community curators not following the provided template (in terms of column order, separators between rows, file extensions, separators between multiple values within one entry) and not adding data consistently (wrong species names, prefixes for identifiers, mixing numerical values and textual descriptions).

The validation files included 82 lines of information, with five entries missing a Rhea, ChEBI, UniProt ID, or with missing provenance (leaving 77 entries). For 52 entries an Enzyme Nomenclature code was provided, and for 70 genes an Ensembl

ID. Fifty reactions contained a Rhea ID, however no reaction formulas were provided for reactions not included in Rhea. Kinetic parameterization data was available for unique SERs for the K_m (37), K_{cat} (16), K_{cat}/K_m (16), Temperature (48), and pH (58). Additional conditions were reported for two entries, and most data was connected to an organism name (74). Provenance for the data was available as PubMed IDs (94) and/or database names (81).

The Quality Control (QC) report showed two entries containing multiple IDs for one substrate, four Enzyme Nomenclature codes not adhering to standards (e.g. missing dots between the numbers, '26113'), many entries using a Reactome ID instead of Rhea, several non-numerical parameters for K_m , K_{cat} , K_{cat}/K_m , pH, or Temperature, and three entries with an unrecognized organism name.

After manually curating the data from groups 2 and 3 based on the QC log (a75243e and 4b85917, the updated Kinetic RDF data model creation script was applied to the originally checked data from group 1, in combination with the data from group 2 and 3. This curation and combination lead to a total of 367 individual SER data points. The remaining curation points were related to interactions not present in Rhea (mostly related to lipid metabolism) and various species currently not included in the Kinetic RDF data model.

8.4 Discussion

Pathway models (PWMs) which capture metabolite classes instead of individual biochemical reactions cannot be used directly for pharmacokinetic and -dynamic data models, however often the detailed biological mechanism is unknown. Therefore, using flexible pathway modeling tools such as PathVisio can allow researchers to capture the information that is known, in combination with knowledge describing partially understood molecular mechanisms.

Another issue can arise when groups within the GPML model are used to connect to the interactions; enzymes are not included in the WP-RDF, metabolic interactions with two side-metabolites will also lead to a loss of information in the conversion to WP-RDf, as well as issues with connecting these compounds to their Rhea ID and reaction equation. Other types of reactions (e.g. signaling, allosteric) cannot easily be taken into account in pharmacokinetic and -dynamic data models, although these interactions could significantly affect intra- and extra-cellular kinetics. OMIM-IDs were added manually as URLs (the only option for textLabels in GPML currently), which might include slight differences in structure (HTTP vs HTTPS, for example).

Future issues for using the provided Kinetic RDF template by community curators are difficult to predict, however, the developed script has been thoroughly vetted with the data gathered throughout this project, to ensure reproducibility for newly collected data.

8.5 Conclusion

This study describes an approach to collect kinetic data in a semantic web model using community approaches, to integrate this data with pathway models. With this work, community curation is supported by bioinformatics approaches to support the harmonization of manually collected data. Not all steps could be fully automated, and the results obtained with this study showed how the knowledge captured in the collected data could be used with maximum efficiency. This work also increased the coverage of biochemical reactions in WikiPathways. The data captured through this project is released as Linked Open Data, to allow the research community to (re)use the knowledge. Furthermore, linked data including provenance information allows curators to find potential inconsistencies between databases. Several pathway models related to Inherited Metabolic Disorders were parameterized with kinetic data, which in the future could be used to help in the identification, diagnosis, and development of (personalized) treatments for these rare metabolic disorders.

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